

BEST PRACTICES IN LIBRARY SERVICES

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Abstract

"Different is not always better but hotter is always different. " Academic libraries are in transition because of changes in the context of higher education. Changes in the world of information are even more radical. Creativity and innovation entail risk and risk is good for libraries. Librarian with low risk tolerances will not be able to sustain the environment necessary creativity or innovation. We must concede that if we want the benefits of creativity and innovation, we must accept the inevitable failure that result from trying something new and welcome them as learning experiences.

Introduction

"Different is not always better but hotter is always different. " {Luce. 2003}

Academic libraries are in transition because of changes in the context of higher education. Changes in the world of information are even more radical: the displacement of paper, the primacy of the search engine, the emergence of the digital lifestyle, and innovative patterns of scholarly communication decreasing reliance on local collections is transforming the library as a physical destination. Traditional measures of library success have begun to be replaced. Given the superiority of other information professional' data management skills, the role of academic librarians will shift towards the enablement of learning. This environment of upheaval will pose both opportunities and services than ever before. People have a seemingly endless array of options for fulfilling their information and community needs. To thrive in this competitive environment librarians must develop novel approaches to designing services and experiences so that they connect with the people they aim to serve, satisfy unmet needs, and achieve enough visibility to gain awareness. Furthermore, the pace of change is always accelerating. Creative and innovative libraries will be able to adapt to these changes, while libraries that don't innovate their services designs on a routine basis will quickly lose

traction. It's true that not everything that's new is by definition good. But since innovation feeds back into creativity even innovative failures are useful in that they allow us to view problems in different lights and to create in different ways.

Present Situation

Students, the future citizens of the country acquire various types of knowledge from various sources and resources available in educational institution, home, Internet, mass media and society at large. Students have misconception that everything is available on the Internet. It is necessary on the part of the librarian and teacher to evoke in students deep interest in library and to develop in them a facility with its use that would adequately serve that interest. It is also generally known fact that too few students enters upon their college with any training in the use of library. Our problem appears to be first of all, to create in our students the desire and if not desire, the need to the use of library and secondly to offer them vast resources of the library as a satisfaction of the desire or need. Librarians have a daunting task of attempting to bring library as close as possible to students. Providing innovative services is one way to attract the students to libraries. Teachers today play a crucial role in society giving their students a foundation of comprehension and knowledge that they will continue to build on throughout their lives.

Innovative Approach For Building understanding of library

If you think of library as a cozy, welcoming space where students can read quietly or browse through a rich collection of texts, you are only partially correct. The fact that libraries are places for storage and quit is only one small part of their purpose. They are in the broadest sense, the backbone of classroom activity. Much of what goes on each day draws from or occurs in or around the resources and space within the library. Students lack understanding that in addition to this there are number of training programs, activities and services offered which can be of great benefit to them. There is an urgent need to develop a positive understanding about the library.

Library Orientation: Making a First Impression with Students.

When a survey of students were conducted as soon as they joined the B. A. B. Com. B. Sc. It was found that almost 90% of them have not received any library orientation. In addition to describing essential content like introduction to staff, purpose of the library, hours, area of library, borrowing procedures, overdue procedures, overview of collection,

rules etc. Special emphasis was given as to how libraries support academic success. Library orientation was organized to find what difficulties students experienced when using library and how that can be minimized.

Information Guides: Libraries Unlimited

Information guides were prepared for reference sources. The aim of guide book was to tell the students what are the reference books, what kind of reference books are available in the library, what kind of information can be obtained from these reference books. These guides not only served as brochure for library but also a guide which student can use for future reference.

Moving beyond Classrooms.- Share and Care Training programs

Computers are widely used now days in a teaching learning process. One of the computer programs which are used mostly is Microsoft Power Point. If you want to make your point powerfully then PowerPoint is the right choice. Microsoft PowerPoint is a feature rich program widely used for designing professional presentation. In Share and Care activities the students during teaching learning activity, share skills with other peer group, for e.g. on a computer there could be two operating and learning simultaneously. Those students who were already well versed with the use of computer technology can help the one who is new in the use of computer; the term care can be referred to the operational part of the hardware and software part of the computer.

Objective

- To develop the understanding of various components of Microsoft Power Point.
- To understand the role of power point in making lessons more interesting.
- To develop skill to use the Power Point.
- To develop skill to make effective search on the internet.
- To develop skill to evaluate websites.

Plans for Actions

1. Identification of talents: in different fields including computer science where tapped student's during the talent search program.

2. Surveying the needs of the students: the students who required the inputs in computer literacy for effective classroom practices were surveyed with the help of student's information sheets.
3. Grouping of the students: the groups of the students for computer training are formed on the basis of their special methods and media of instruction and accordingly a mentor is provided to the group.
4. Planning the training schedule: the training schedule is planned keeping in view the overall academic planning of the institution and availability of leisure time for the students and the mentors.

The training period is generally for one week with one and half hours interaction every day. During this period the students are acquainted with different parts of computer and their function and Microsoft PowerPoint menus during this training program lectures was given by librarian on how to evaluate websites and how to make effective search on the internet.

Unfortunately for students today and many teachers in our workforce remember the libraries and librarians as they encountered in the past, bringing to mind former recollections of libraries as warehouses. And librarians as resource providers and they lack understanding of the learning and teaching role of the librarian. All these services are an effort to change present perceptions of the instructional role of librarian and to build positive understanding about the library.

Innovative approach to make students aware of sources of library

For many references librarians, the perceived survival of the library is threatened by the prevalence of the Internet. This fear is due to their inability to picture the function of the library in any way other than a gateway to book and journals. The majority of students use the library's access to the Internet. With the proliferation of electronic resources, many students lack any exposure to traditional reference sources, print journal indices and card catalogs. This exposure is needed to establish these resources as vital elements in information-seeking behaviour. Without that exposure it may not be possible to convince them to use these resources. A different approach must then be explored. Reference source are one of the untapped reserves of library. As students have different needs for information, it is necessary for students to identify different sources that differ in the arrangement and

content. Student was made aware of the sources available in the library providing specialized services making use of the sources.

Who am I?

The aims of this project were (1) For the students: (a) To revise vocabulary (b) To familiarize with dictionaries and their macro- and microstructure; (c) To increase awareness of the scope of an ideal dictionary for these B. Ed students - and its limitations.

This is weekly service in which one word is selected and following information for the same is given Meaning, Etymology, Synonyms, Antonyms, Word in Hindi, and Word in Marathi.

Web file

Web usage for academic research is increasing rapidly. Because the quality of sources on the Internet varies tremendously, techniques are needed to evaluate Web resources. Some traditional print techniques for evaluation are still appropriate, but different techniques are also needed to address this new medium. Students when asked to do research go to Google and search. In order to make the students aware that not all the information available on the net is authentic this service was planned. According to this monthly a website was selected and what information can be obtained from that website was given. Authenticity of the website was established by giving write up about author, coverage of subject, treatment of subject.

Newspaper Learning

Main objective of the service was to make student aware of educational value of the newspaper. Some newspaper have very interesting feature that can be used for teaching learning process.

For e.g. The Times of India had a feature learning with Times, Economic Times had a feature *E'T* in the Classroom, Employment News also gives information about different careers? All these features were identified and put up on the notice board.

An analysis of the responses indicated that as a result of their studies, students generally felt themselves to be better informed. Many felt that using the newspaper had increased their

vocabulary levels, widened their scope of information, and influenced them to read more. The results indicate that appropriate and enthusiastic use of a previously unexplored medium can bring about positive changes in students' attitudes.

Information Sharing

The college initiated a new activity of article review by the students. The main objective behind this activity is to orient (be students to review articles from educational journals. The activity serves dual purpose of reviewing and making the students aware about research and problems faced in education. Provision in the timetable was made to read the article review in the assembly. The students referred to different articles and journals. Few research articles were also read out. The student community gained a lot of information as the articles were either related to their topics in various papers or research articles creating an awareness of various educational problems.

Innovative approach to improve the reading habit of the student

'Reading to learn' is an essential tool for life-long learning. Promoting a reading culture Among students is therefore one of the key tasks in the curriculum reform with the aim to Strengthen students' learning capabilities. Through pleasurable reading, students have opportunities to apply skills to meaningful contexts, build general and content-specific knowledge, experience fluency with connected text, and. of course, develop the lifetime reading habit. Our students, therefore, need opportunities in college and at home to enjoy "real" reading us a valued and worthwhile activity. Easy access to reading materials is one of the important factors in cultivating reading habits in students. Students would spend more time on reading if reading activities are actively promoted and a reading atmosphere created.

Book review club

One reason to start book club is lo broaden reading experience and expose students to books outside their usual interest. Therefore, we decided not to limit our choice of books of any particular genre. Members would be encouraged to bring book suggestions to each meeting and, as a group; we would make a selection for the following month. Interlibrary loans would be our primary means of obtaining books for the hook club members. A group of students were formed in which one acted as coordinator or leader and others were member. The exchange of ideas and shared reading experiences truly create a special bond within the

group. After one lively discussion one of our student said that she felt confident that she could openly express her opinions without fearing that the other group members might take her comments personally. The challenge for any book club leader is to provide a setting where every participant feels that level of comfort.

Maximum Library Reference Award

B. Ed education at the University of Mumbai occurs in an environment where teaching, research and service are integrated and mutually enterprising. The K. J. Somaiya B. Ed college annual Maximum Library Reference Award Program recognizes B. Ed students who demonstrate extraordinary skill and creativity in the application of library and information resources to original research projects.

Evaluation Criteria

Successful project will:

- ❖ Make extensive, creative use of library services, resources, and collection in any format.
- ❖ Demonstrate effective application of information literacy and fluency principles.

Determining information needs, evaluating and analyzing information managing, organizing and synthesizing information applying information in the context of the research project, communicating information in formats appropriate to an academic audience making responsible use of information by providing appropriate and accurate citations and credits, show evidence of significant personal knowledge in the methods of research and inquiry. Demonstrate originality of thought, mastery of content appropriate to class level, clear writing and overall quality of presentation.

Future innovative program

We are outfitting our schools, libraries and homes with electronic technologies—but are we preparing our students and teachers for the onslaught of information that is provided by these technologies? What happens when the student can get more information from the internet than previously conveyed by a teacher or a textbook? What should a student do when faced with so many informational possibilities? Which of the information is credible and which is not? With the provision of so much more information, and therefore more misinformation, everyone where they are in the education system or not must have not only

reading skills and computer skills but information skills, too. The term information literacy, sometimes referred to as information competency, is generally defined as the ability to access, evaluate, organize, and use information from a variety of sources. Being information literate requires knowing how to clearly define a subject or area of investigation; select the appropriate terminology that expresses the concept or subject under investigation; formulate a search strategy that takes into consideration different sources of information and the variable ways that information is organized; analyze the data collected for value, relevancy, quality, and suitability; and subsequently turn information into knowledge (ALA 1989). This involves a deeper understanding of how and where to find information, the ability to judge whether that information is meaningful, and ultimately, how best that information can be incorporated to address the problem or issue at hand. Librarian in collaboration with faculty member is developing an information literacy instruction program to develop research skills of student teachers.

Conclusion

Tajmahal was not built in a day, nor can we expect a sudden burst of enthusiasm in desire to use library as a result of this innovative services. As we know from the time immemorial our country has looked upon the teacher not just as an instructor but a molder of human personality. A teacher is a transmitter of knowledge but also an innovator, agent of change and social engineer. The values that they impart leave an indelible imprint upon students. Even if we are successful to at least make one teacher aware of the importance and use of library many future students will be automatically will became aware of it. So it is necessary for librarian and teacher to collaborate, to experiment and be ready with answers when the opportunity comes.

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